

Epidemiology of Cholera in Nigeria: A Scoping Review

Ruppee Orighomisan Prince-Edward

Development Initiative For Community Impact (DICI), Nigeria.

*. **Corresponding author:** Ruppee Orighomisan Prince-Edward, Development Initiative For Community Impact (DICI), Nigeria. Phone: +2347068576006. Email: ruppeed@yahoo.com.

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Abstract

Cholera continues to be a global public health problem and a sign of societal inequality and underdevelopment, despite the fact that it may be predicted and avoided. Cholera is a severe diarrheal infection caused by eating food or water infected with *Vibrio cholera* bacterium. Only two of *V. cholerae*'s serogroups, O1 and O139, are known to generate outbreaks. Nigeria leads Africa in documented cholera cases, a pandemic that has increased since 2020. In 2021, Nigeria accounted for 88% of documented deaths and 78% of reported cases in Africa, indicating no significant improvement. Local communities in Nigeria accounted for 80% of deaths, according to recently released World Health Organization data. Long-term solutions to the cholera epidemic include economic growth, universal access to clean water, and basic sanitation. The primary methods for preventing cholera are to immunize people against the disease with oral cholera vaccinations and to give clean water and proper sanitation to communities that do not already have access to these essentials. The ongoing cholera outbreak in Nigeria can be attributed to a lack of clean water and sanitation infrastructure, open defecation, and poor hygiene practices. This report gives a synopsis of the epidemiology of cholera in Nigeria based on available relevant scientific literature.

Keywords: Cholera, Epidemic, Water, Sanitation, Nigeria

Introduction

Cholera is a global public health threat and a sign of societal inequality and underdevelopment, despite the fact that it can be predicted and avoided (1). The World Health Organization (1) defines cholera as an acute diarrheal infection caused by eating food or water contaminated with the *Vibrio cholera* bacteria. Estuaries and coastal waters are typical habitats for these bacteria. People get *V. cholerae* after consuming infected beverages or meals (2). Symptoms may emerge between 12 hours and 5 days after consuming contaminated food or drink. Cholera can infect both adults and children and, if left untreated, can kill within hours (1).

The cholera bacteria has hundreds of strains or "serogroups," with *V. cholerae* "serogroups" O1 and O139 being the only two strains known to cause outbreaks and epidemics (1,2). The disorders induced by these two "serogroups" are similar. *Vibrio cholera* can be seen in the feces for 1-10 days, and most infected patients do not develop symptoms until

several days after infection. As a result, the germs are released into the environment, where they may infect others. However, the disease can be eradicated in locations where the entire population has consistent and assured access to safe drinking water, sanitary facilities, and proper hygiene habits.

According to evidence, there are between 1.3 and 4.0 million cholera cases worldwide each year, with 21000 to 143000 deaths caused by the disease (1,3). In 2017, the World Health Organization launched a global cholera control strategy named "*Ending Cholera: A Global Roadmap to 2030*" with the goal of reducing cholera-related fatalities by 90%. Seven years later, illness burdens continue to climb, particularly in Nigeria. This report gives a synopsis of the epidemiology of cholera in Nigeria based on available relevant scientific literature.

History of Cholera Outbreak

Despite the fact that cholera has existed for millennia, it rose to prominence in the nineteenth century

following a fatal outbreak in India. The first cholera pandemic came from the "Ganges Delta" in 1817, with an outbreak caused by infected rice in Jessore, India. The disease rapidly spread throughout most of India, modern-day Myanmar, and modern-day Sri Lanka via trade routes created by Europeans (2). Since then, there have been countless outbreaks and seven global cholera pandemics (1,2). Cholera is now considered endemic in various nations.

Since the disease's first outbreak in 1972, Nigeria has experienced annual cholera outbreaks (3). These outbreaks are most common during the rainy season, when the disease is more prone to spread due to inadequate drainage systems, poor hygiene habits, and a lack of access to safe drinking water (4,5). According to Ayetoto-Oladehinde (6), Nigeria has the most recorded cases of cholera in Africa. In 2020, the incidence of the cholera epidemic quadrupled compared to prior years. In 2021, Nigeria accounted for 88% of documented deaths and 78% of reported cases in Africa, indicating no significant improvement. In 2021, Africa experienced a 29% decrease in reported cases, a 52% decrease in reported deaths, and a 1.9% decrease in the case fatality ratio.

In 2010, Nigeria's Northern area faced a large cholera epidemic, with 3,000 confirmed cases and 781 fatalities (5). A decade or so later, Nigeria reported 100,000 probable cholera cases, the highest figure in recent years (7). From January to July 2021, the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control reported 111,062 cholera infections and 3,604 deaths in the country. These values were greater than those reported for 2020.

Furthermore, Nigeria reported 23,550 suspected cases in 2022, including 583 cholera cases, higher than the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Cameroon, Malawi, and Somalia (7-9). Local communities in Nigeria accounted for 80% of deaths, according to recently released World Health Organization data (1). From September 2022 to December 2022, six states accounted for 84% of all cholera cases in Nigeria, with Borno State leading the way with 12,496 cases and 394 deaths (288 confirmed, 106 suspected) in seventeen of twenty-seven Local Government Areas (10). Yobe State came in second with 1,888 cases, while Katsina State followed with 1,632. Taraba had 1,142 instances; Gombe State had 1,407 cases; and Kano State had 1,131 (9). Furthermore, 52 percent of cholera patients in 2022 were female, with men accounting for 48 percent. The fatality rate was 2.5 percent of recorded cases in 33 Nigerian states. The majority of those affected were children aged five to fourteen (9).

According to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, the Cumulative Epidemiology Summary for 2023

shows that 3,683 suspected cases, including 128 deaths (CFR 3.5%), have been reported from 31 states (11). Since the beginning of the year, the under-5 age group has been the most afflicted, followed by the 5-14 age group, which includes both boys and females (11). Furthermore, 51 percent of all suspected cases are men and 49 percent are women (11). Zamfara State led with 914 cases, accounting for 25% of all suspected cases in the country's 31 states that have reported cases of cholera (11). This was closely followed by Cross River State, which had 718 cases, with Obubra LGA (515 cases) accounting for 14% of all suspected cases reported nationwide. In 2023, Katsina State had 343 cases, Bayelsa State had 319 cases, Ogun State had 295 cases, Ebonyi State had 236 cases, and Niger State had 195 cases, accounting for 57% of the suspected cases. In comparison, probable cholera cases in 2023 decreased by 85 percent from what was reported during Epidemiology Week 52 in 2022. Furthermore, the overall number of deaths reported in 2023 has decreased by 79% compared to figures reported in 2022 (11).

Epidemiology, Risk Factors and Disease Burden

Cholera can be either epidemic or endemic (1). Cholera-endemic areas are those where confirmed cases of the disease have been discovered during the last three years. It is vital to recognize that both endemic and non-endemic countries can experience cholera outbreaks. Furthermore, the two most important epidemiologic aspects of cholera are its proclivity to cause violence outbreaks and to spark pandemics that may eventually infect numerous countries (12).

Cholera transmission is strongly associated with a lack of access to sanitation facilities and clean water. At-risk areas may include peri-urban slums and camps for internally displaced people or refugees (1). The consequences of a humanitarian crisis, such as the disruption of water and sanitary infrastructure or the relocation of people to tiny, crowded camps, can raise the risk of disease transmission during an outbreak. However, there is no evidence that uninfected dead bodies started the epidemics.

Furthermore, prior cholera epidemics in Nigeria have been analyzed in light of the vulnerability created by either armed conflict or natural catastrophes such as floods (13). Humanitarian crises are frequently accompanied by hostilities, resulting in insufficient access to food, water, and sanitary facilities, accelerating the spread of infectious diseases such as cholera. Conflicts also reduce access to medical care and humanitarian assistance. While the Boko Haram

militancy has devastated the North-East region for over a decade, the North-Western region has seen some of the bloodiest bandit attacks in a long time. As a result, millions of displaced people from the sixteen states in these regions have faced significant food, portable water, shelter, and medical treatment shortages [5,14]. This has also led to numerous reports of cholera outbreaks in these locations.

In recent years, the World Health Organization has received a large number of reports of cholera. In 2022, 44 countries reported 472,697 cases and 2,349 deaths (15). These figures deviate from the estimated disease burden because many cases went unreported due to surveillance system shortcomings and concerns about how the epidemic might effect trade and tourism.

Steps taken by the Nigerian Government to Curb Cholera Outbreaks

In response to an epidemic at Borno State's displaced persons' camps in 2017, the National Primary Healthcare Development Agency and other partners carried out oral cholera immunization campaigns. (16) The oral cholera vaccine is not included in Nigeria's standard vaccination program. It is not completely effective against cholera and does not protect against other foodborne or waterborne illnesses. It is not a permanent solution to cholera, but rather a bridge between emergency response and long-term cholera control. To combat the outbreak, reactive oral cholera vaccine campaigns were launched in Borno in 2017 (16).

In 2019, the Nigerian government, led by the Federal Ministry of Water Resources, distributed 510,663 litres of water per day to 39 localities in Adamawa state, accounting for 50% of cholera cases. It implemented initiatives to enhance water availability, basic sanitation, and hygiene habits. It also offered mobile solar-powered boreholes. The International Organization for Migration kept 58 solar-powered boreholes in Borno State and drilled 11 additional ones in 2019. It also renovated ten and connected them to solar electricity. Outbreak investigation teams from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) performed health education programs following the confirmation of cholera outbreaks. The United Nations Education Fund (UNICEF) encouraged communities in cholera hotspots to chlorinate their water supplies. This helped an estimated 4.5 million people in Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe states, including 680,000 displaced individuals in cities (16).

In 2022, following an increase in cholera cases, the multi-sectoral National Cholera Technical Working Group (TWG) collaborated with partners to assist

affected states with risk communication, active case search, case management, and water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) interventions (17). The NCDC-led multisectoral TWG comprises representatives from the Federal Ministries of Environment and Water Resources, the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA), WHO, and UNICEF.

From January 2024 to the present, 1,141 suspected and 65 confirmed cases of cholera, including 30 deaths, have been recorded from 96 LGAs throughout 30 states. Bayelsa, Zamfara, Abia, Cross River, Bauchi, Delta, Katsina, Imo, Nasarawa, and Lagos are the ten states that account for 90% of cholera cases. As a result, the Nigerian government, in collaboration with other international organizations, provided assistance to the affected states in the form of risk communication, active case search, laboratory diagnosis, case management, response commodities, water sanitation and hygiene (WASH) interventions, and the distribution of cholera awareness jingles in both English and local languages (18).

Cholera Vaccines in Nigeria

The recent cholera outbreak in June 2024 served as a wake-up call for the Nigerian government, with the NCDC director emphasizing the importance of using vaccinations and other preventive measures to reduce the spread of the acute diarrheal infection. The Vaccine Alliance, Gavi, announced on Twitter that cholera vaccines would soon be available in Nigeria to help stem the deadly and ongoing illness outbreak. According to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, Nigeria has ordered additional cholera vaccinations from donor agencies, however the delivery date is yet undetermined (19-21).

Prevention and Control

Water and Sanitation Interventions: Long-term solutions to the cholera epidemic include economic growth, universal access to clean water, and basic sanitation. Long-term sustainable water sanitation and hygiene solutions are being implemented as part of environmental improvement initiatives (22). These solutions ensure the use of safe drinking water, basic sanitation, and proper hygiene practices. Such methods not only prevent cholera, but also a variety of other water-borne infections, as well as aid in the achievement of educational, poverty, and nutritional goals. The water sanitation and hygiene solutions for cholera complement the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 6).

Treatment: The cholera sickness is easily treated. Most patients can benefit from oral rehydration solution (ORS), which can be delivered quickly and effectively. The World Health Organization/United Nations Children Fund ORS standard sachet can be dissolved in one liter (L) of purified water. On the first day, adult patients may require up to six liters of ORS to treat mild dehydration (1). Patients who are very dehydrated, on the other hand, must receive intravenous fluids as soon as possible or risk developing shock. Patients should also be administered the appropriate drugs to reduce the severity of the diarrhea, reduce the amount of rehydration fluids necessary, and limit the length of *V. cholerae* excretion in their stool. Furthermore, it is recommended that all patients begin eating regularly scheduled, well-prepared local foods as soon as it is safe to do so (1,22). It's also crucial to promote breastfeeding.

During a cholera outbreak, rapid access to treatment is critical. Communities should have access to oral rehydration, including designated oral rehydration points, as well as larger medical facilities that provide 24-hour treatment and IV fluids. This is because when patients receive quick and proper care, the fatality rate does not surpass 1%. Zinc is an important supplemental medication for children under the age of five since it shortens the duration of diarrhea and may prevent future episodes of acute watery diarrhea (1,22).

Community Engagement: This entails involving individuals and communities in the design and implementation of programs. The culture, practices, and beliefs of the local community greatly impact promoting behaviors such as good hand washing with soap, food preparation and storage, and the safe disposal of children's excrement. To protect guests from infection, funeral practices for cholera deaths must also be modified (1,22). Community engagement during an outbreak must be maintained through increased communication about potential hazards, cholera symptoms, preventative measures, when and where to report cases, and the importance of seeking early medical assistance when symptoms appear. Community participation is vital in the development of programs that address needs, such as when and where to get care.

Furthermore, the primary methods of cholera prevention are immunizing people against the disease with oral cholera vaccinations and providing clean water and proper sanitation to communities that do not currently have access to these essentials (1,22). Proper food hygiene and health education are also important. It is critical to educate populations about essential hygiene practices. These include the need to

properly prepare and store food, as well as wash hands with soap before and after peeing. Furthermore, enhancing surveillance and early warning systems is required to discover early instances in an outbreak and execute control measures as soon as possible.

Conclusion

Cholera is intimately associated with impoverished rural settings where people frequently lack access to clean water, poor nutrition, and inadequate sanitation. It is frequently referred to as "the disease of poverty". Even though the Nigerian government has taken some steps to manage the epidemic by demanding emergency vaccine doses when necessary. More efforts are still required, as earlier initiatives mainly targeted afflicted areas. The continuing growth in cholera outbreaks can be attributed to a lack of clean water and sanitation facilities, open defecation, and poor hygiene practices. In the absence of effective WASH practices, Nigeria would remain vulnerable to cholera epidemics and the resulting suffering and deaths. Nigeria launched an action plan in 2016 to eliminate open defecation by 2025. The strategy aims for improved community-specific approaches to complete sanitation, as well as fair access to water, sanitation, and hygiene services. However, nearly a decade later, Nigeria is still far from achieving its aim.

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